

THE ROLE OF PUBLIC INFORMATION POLICY IN ENHANCING THE EFFICIENCY OF STATE ADMINISTRATIONS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *Information policy is important in our country, and to increase its efficiency, it is necessary to have experienced and specialist forces. This article presents the steps taken to improve the effectiveness of the information policy of public administration in Uzbekistan, its problems, solutions and recommendations for the future.*

Keywords: *Uzbekistan, public administration, efficiency, improvement, information, policy, role, article.*

Public information policy plays a crucial role in enhancing the efficiency of state administrations in Uzbekistan. By ensuring transparency and accessibility of information, the government can promote accountability, improve decision-making processes, and build trust with citizens. Effective public information policy can also help streamline communication between government agencies and the public, leading to more efficient service delivery and better governance overall. In Uzbekistan, implementing a robust public information policy can lead to increased efficiency in state administrations by:

Promoting transparency: Making government information readily available to the public can help prevent corruption and hold public officials accountable for their actions. This transparency can also foster trust between the government and citizens.

Improving decision-making processes: Access to accurate and timely information can help policymakers make informed decisions that are in the best interest of the country and its citizens. Public information policy can ensure that decision-makers have access to relevant data and analysis.

Enhancing communication: Clear and accessible information can facilitate communication between government agencies, leading to smoother coordination and collaboration. This can help streamline administrative processes and avoid duplication of efforts.

Empowering citizens: Providing citizens with information about government activities and policies empowers them to hold officials accountable and participate in the democratic process. Open access to information can also help citizens understand their rights and responsibilities.

Overall, a strong public information policy can contribute to the efficiency and effectiveness of state administrations in Uzbekistan by fostering transparency, improving decision-making, enhancing communication, and empowering citizens.

Responses to political and economic challenges are associated with the construction of a management model with significant mobilization potential and high adaptive capabilities. Against the backdrop of global political and economic instability, the problems of the effectiveness of public administration, on the one hand, and the effectiveness of its reform in order to optimize national development, on the other, have become a priority for many countries of the world, including Uzbekistan. Knowledge of the criteria for the effectiveness of both public administration

itself and its reform will allow reaching a new level of understanding of administrative policy, will allow predicting trends in global and domestic political processes, the challenges facing modern Uzbekistan determine public administration as a dynamic system capable of adapting the institutions of state power and, above all, the executive, to the rapidly changing needs of society in the process of structural reforms. Identification of ways and means to improve the efficiency of reforming the state actualizes the topic of the study. The purpose of the study is to identify the content of reforming the public administration of modern Uzbekistan. In accordance with the goal, the following tasks are being solved that determine the structure of the work:

- to identify the features of understanding public administration in modern political thought;
- to determine the specifics of reforming public administration in the context of the transition to a post-industrial society;
- to clarify the criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of modern public administration and administrative reforms;
- to explore the vectors of public administration reform in the country;
- to reveal the features of reforming public administration in Uzbekistan at the present stage;
- to analyze the directions of reforming public administration at the regional level. The object of the study is public administration at the present stage of development of society. The subject of the study is the content of reforming the public administration of modern Uzbekistan.

Theoretical and methodological foundations of the work. The political changes that are taking place in modern Uzbekistan and are in many ways unique, create an urgent need to design a new management model that has a high mobilization and development potential. The basis of this model is the rethinking of the role and functions of the state and civil service, which is taking place in the course of modern administrative reforms. The result of the implementation of the new public administration should be an innovative and “efficient state”.

The scientific novelty of the research is as follows:

-It is substantiated that in modern political science, public administration in the context of the transition to a post-industrial society is considered as a syncretism of the management of a state organization and population management:

It is concluded that the reform of public administration in modern conditions is associated with the transition from the Weberian model of rational bureaucracy to the model of civil servants, which corresponds to the interests of the formation of a post-industrial society;

- It was revealed that the effectiveness of reforming public administration is determined by the degree of autonomy of citizens from bureaucratic red tape and arbitrariness in the process of receiving the services provided by the state;

-It was determined that in the 90s of the XX century in Uzbekistan there was an understanding of the vectors of reforming public administration, aimed at creating conditions for the transition to the model of civil entity, the essence of which is filling traditional functions with “service” content, is characteristic of the current stage of public administration reform;

-It was revealed that the reform of public administration at the regional level is aimed at increasing the responsibility of regional state structures for the quality of services provided by the state authorities to the population.

The theoretical significance of the study lies in the fact that the main provisions of the study can contribute to the introduction into scientific circulation of new information about the effectiveness of reforming public administration in a situation of growing global financial crisis

and outlining the possibilities of using the acquired knowledge for a comprehensive study of public administration problems. The conclusions of the work can contribute to the deepening of theoretical ideas about the modern understanding of public administration and its role in periods of transformation of political systems.

The practical significance of the study lies in the fact that the results obtained in the work can be useful to public authorities, local governments, public organizations in political practice in the development and adjustment of political and managerial decisions to strengthen statehood, identify new trends and tasks for the further democratic development of modern Uzbek states.

The research materials can become the basis for the construction of specialized training courses in the field of political science, the theory of public administration. The research materials can be used when teaching special courses in the specialties “Political Science”, “State and Municipal Administration”. The main thing in the management of the future is the adaptation of the management mechanism to changes in the conditions of management, the dynamics of the development of society and the needs of people. Management resources (authorities, personnel, finance, information support) should become the most important material base of state administration. The effectiveness of management depends on this. Efficiency is a qualitative indicator of management. So, we can summarize: in the current conditions of the formation of a strong, capable democratic state in Uzbekistan, the stability of society and the sustainable development of the economy are impossible without the broad support of the population, without its social consolidation.

In conclusion, a robust public information policy is essential for promoting good governance practices and improving the efficiency of state administrations in Uzbekistan. By prioritizing transparency, accountability, and citizen engagement, the government can strengthen its democratic institutions and better serve the needs of its people.

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